

Religion, Ethnicity and National Integration in Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigeria is a mixture of many ethnic groups and diverse religious orientations. This heterogeneous nature of the country in terms of cultural affiliations, religious dichotomies have corresponding effects on national integration especially when it appears ethnic tension and religious fundamentalism would induce sentiments that lead to disintegration. This paper examines critically the concepts of Religion and Ethnicity as they relate to national integration. The various efforts in integrating Nigeria are discussed to include, Federal character, establishment of unity schools, National Youth Service Corps Scheme and quota system. Secondary data was used for information gathering. The findings of the work reveal that ethnicity and religion are key issues in national integration that political elites use to camouflage their incompetency, corruption, leadership failure and loss of political interest. The consequences are various ethnic conflicts, prejudices, religious crises, insecurity and agitation for separation and secession which do not augur well for national integration and development. Suggestions are made to include restructuring the federal system of government, equity and fair distribution of appointments placing of less emphasis on religion and ethnicity on official documents and harvesting sports solidarity for national integration in order to give way for development to thrive at the state and local levels.

Keywords: Ethnicity, Religion, National Integration

Introduction

Nigeria is made up of different ethnic groups. It is speculated that Nigeria has at least two hundred and fifty ethnic groups (National Teachers Institute [NTI]).¹ Okwudiba Nnoli identifies 374 ethnic groups in Nigeria.² These ethnic groups lived together before the amalgamation of 1914. Contrary to the belief that it is the British amalgamation that compelled Nigerians to live together, these ethnic groups existed on the principle of interdependence. The miracle of amalgamation only fixed the boundaries of these groups and stopped the expansion and conquest of most dominant ones against the minorities. Nevertheless, the amalgamation made Nigeria a single country with different ethnic groups coming together under a single name Nigeria.

Harrison Otuekong Ataide and Martins Tom Enebong are convinced that the diverse nature of ethnic composition of the Nigerian state is responsible for the disunity and lack of peaceful coexistence and integration, sustainable development and progress of the country at large. They further identified the spirit of ethnicity and ethnic politics since independence as the bane of “administrative, economic, social development in Nigeria”. They concluded that national integration in Nigeria which is sine-qua-non to national development is technically contingent upon overcoming the challenges of ethnicity.³

Apart from the challenges of ethnicity, the strong forces of alien religions; Christianity and Islam threaten the national cohesion as they compete to eliminate and gain dominion over the other religions. While the aliens competitively struggle to annihilate the traditional religion to exhibit its supremacy, conflicts abound as the two have not come to terms on how they would share the Nigerian population in peace and achieve a cohesive nation. The introduction of the Sharia law in some northern states and the resultant violence that followed are other bad signals for the survival of Nigeria as a single entity. That is to say some concerned Nigerians feel strongly that Nigeria should continue to exist as a single entity with a national culture where cohesion and national unity will be achieved for better Nigeria and development.

Nevertheless, some other Nigerians who believe that it is still possible to remain united, on certain conditions, are calling for political restructuring of the nation, which they believe would guarantee a better relationship amongst the various federating ethnic groups than it is now. In most nations that are heterogeneous in population, there cannot be growth without integration Any nation built on ethnic cleavage which allows a

group to usurp all powers at the expense of other ethnic groupings is doomed and is fast forwarding to disintegration. It is against this background that this paper focuses on the concepts of religion and ethnicity as they relate to national integration in Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification

The Concept of Religion

The concept, religion has many definitions reflecting the definers' background and environment. In this work Religion is the belief and practice of a people in their efforts to manage the relationship that exists between the spiritual and the physical worlds with man at the centre regulating the relationship between the two worlds. Religion is the notion of a transcendental power which regulates human activities and controls events.⁴ In Nigeria, Omotaye Olorode rightly observed that the ruling class has imposed Christianity and Islam as national religions pretending that indigenous religions do not exist anymore and invoking both in their intra-class negotiations. Religion has thus become a powerful force that can be, and is being, manipulated and politicised.⁵ The competition between the two alien religions has constituted security threat to the country's integration.

The Concept of Ethnicity

Ethnicity derives from ethnic group. According to Ademola Poopola, an ethnic group is a group of people that are identified by a common language, common descent or lineage and cultural affinity. Ethnic groups are social formations distinguished by communal character of their boundaries, the relevant communal factors being language and culture.⁶ Alubo explains that Ethnic group is a nominal concept in relation to one's circumstances of birth, or what sociologists call ascribed status in which individuals have no choice in being born in a particular ethnic group.⁷ It is identification and over conscious consideration of these ethnic identities that breeds ethnicity in multi-ethnic nation.

Ethnicity is the use of ethnic advantage against others to gain access to employment opportunities, political appointment and other gainful opportunities in a society with plural ethnic groupings. Osaghae has it that "Ethnicity is the employment or mobilisation of ethnic identity and difference to gain advantage in situations of competition, conflict, or cooperation".⁸ Ethnicity is therefore, the conscious identification with one's ethnic group to the detriment of other ethnic groups in terms of power sharing, natural resources and opportunities. It involves deliberate rejection of principles of nationalism, equity and fairness when it comes to national issues. It connotes the feeling of ethnic pride and unhealthy competition in the face of scarce or mismanaged resources and opportunities.

The Concept of National Integration

Integration is the attainment within a territory of a sense of community and of institutions and practices strong enough and widespread enough to assure for a long-time dependable expectation of a peaceful community. National integration on the other hand means the unification of apparently separate groups into an indivisible whole.⁹ National integration connotes bringing together of various ethnic and social groups into a harmonious and working relationship with the loyalty of the country placed above any other loyalty. Guobadia explains that the process of national integration is an attempt to forge a coming together and attitudes of cooperation and national loyalty among the various groups in the country.¹⁰ It presupposes that the loyalty of the heterogeneous nature of one's ethnic composition is abandoned. The aim is to make citizens live together and reason as a single entity despite the ethnic diversity. This is achieved through conscious efforts and recognition of the importance of the existence of others in the country. National integration suggests a state where there is a high level of amicable social interaction among the various peoples of a nation and where they are admitted into or deployed in the country's institutions without regard to sex, class, ethnic groups, religious or political leaning.

Ethnicity presupposes the existence of multi ethnic cultural identities in a society. In a multi-ethnic society like Nigeria, ethnicity manifests itself through the following:

(i) **Ethnic Identity:** Ethnic identity precedes ethnicity. That is the consciousness created in the minds of a people as belonging to a group by birth, culture and common purpose. This results in formation of ethnic associations or organisations.

Ethnicity is seen manifested in diverse ways. Alubo has it that:

Such ethnically motivated action through the building of schools might take the form of agitation for greater share or participation in local, regional or nationwide affairs, protests or even violence in expressing these, so long as such actions are ethnically motivated. It may also involve accepting some challenges in addressing and redressing identified problems such as combating illiteracy, providing infrastructure such as safe drinking water and access roads and in some cases, economic activities such as communal ownership of rice and food processing mills. In effect, ethnicity is not by definition negative or antithetical to the nation building project.¹¹

(ii) **Ethnic conflicts and religious violence:** ethnic conflicts are conflicts which ensue from situations in which people from different ethnic groups decide to employ their ethnic differences in pursuing competing interests.¹² Etanibi Alemika believes that colonial and post-colonial Nigeria contained certain conditions that provide fertile grounds for ethnicity that results in to ethnic conflicts and religious violence. These include:

Ethnic and religious pluralism; economic deprivation and injustice; youth unemployment; gross income inequalities; discrimination, ineffective government that may fuel and manipulate ethnic and religious differences and the existence of ethnic and religious entrepreneurs who seek to benefit from politicisation of identities by offering ethnic and religious interpretations of public life and public policy.¹³

Most recently, the nation is indeed ravaged by insecurity caused by Fulani herdsmen, terrorists and bandits. The inaction by government at the centre, appears a promotion of ethnicity. Some Nigerians are thus left with no other options than to suspect and accuse the central administration of being sympathetic towards the perpetrators of the violence against the nation. Allegations derive strengths from the fact that the president of Nigeria is from the same Fulani ethnic folk. It is very clear that the Fulani in West Africa have taken advantage of the weak and ethnic biased leadership unleashed havoc on ethnic minorities in the country.

Religion, Ethnicity and National integration in Nigeria

Alubo once averred that ethnicity is a concept which at once conjures up images and warfare as well as images of groups proudly attired in costumes which distinguish them from others. Both for good or ill, this concept is integral to Nigeria's nation building project and its overall development process, as such is a recurring decimal in the annals of its nationhood.¹⁴ Alemika agrees with this when he observed that ethnicity has objective and subjective dimensions. The former defines people in terms of their cultural heritage, practices and orientations which signifies differences, which may be harnessed either for development or destruction.¹⁵ This promotes formation of ethnic based associations for the protection of group economic, social and political interests. Kukah supports this assertion when he says: "Ethnic consciousness did have its own benefits as a propelling force at least in the early history of Nigeria. At a time... it was these tribal unions which filled the gap by rallying communities for the provision of education to their people as a means of catching up with other favoured ethnic groups."¹⁶

Today, many educated people in Nigeria are beneficiaries of such community schools. Ethnicity constitutes a way in which people think of themselves and others and make sense of the world around them. It refers to both the call addressed to ethnic groups and their social identity. At the same time, it also refers to set of social relations within which social groupings such as men, women, poor, rich, young, old relate to each other. More significantly, it refers to specific power relations at the same time as it refers to cultural relations. Alubo explains that in everyday interaction, ethnic origin gives one some sense of identity and through common cultural symbols, some solidarity as well.¹⁷

The objective dimension of ethnicity on the other hand involves the politicisation and mobilisation of ethnic differences within a multi ethnic society. It equally involves the evaluation of ones' ethnicity in relation to

other ethnic groups and use of the evaluation as the basis of relationships with members of other groups thereby generating the feeling of “we” versus “they”. When this happens, the noble ideas of objective ethnic identification are defeated.¹⁸ Kukah acknowledges that in addition to educational institutions, these associations established health institutions and carried out other developmental projects in their communities. He however, lamented that the zeal with which the associations started was changed after independence. He explains: “When the British politicised access to the bureaucracy, ethnicity then assumed a new garb which would later transform it in to a weapon of battle, not a tool of self, communal and, subsequently national development and integration”.¹⁹ At times the launching of appeal funds in the pretence that a community wishes to build their institutions are umbrellas under which funds are raised for acquisition of weapons (arms and ammunitions) of war or ethnic conflicts.

Over the years, there have been reoccurring ethnic conflicts in Nigeria. The most occurring crises are Urhobo- Itsekiri, Ife-Modakeke, Tiv-Jukun, Hausa and indigenous people of plateau State. Recently, the conflicts have taken a new dimension as the Fulani herdsmen are leading in ethnic cleansing to address their frustration. This has generated tension, ethnic consciousness, identities and of course ethnicity to defend their territories. Though, ethnicity had existed in the precolonial and post-colonial periods it is worse in the contemporary Nigeria. It is no exaggeration to say that key issues in national integration are religion and ethnicity manifesting in diverse ways that have threatened the unity of Nigeria.

Religion and ethnicity are good veritable verdures through which terrorism, leadership failure, incompetency, corruption are concealed to create tension and distract the less informed majority of Nigerians from addressing their real problems. It appears political elites take advantage of the weaknesses of religions and lack of political education to perpetuate themselves in power while common citizens kill themselves in the name of religion and ethnic conflicts. The consequence is that the nation is indeed ravaged by insecurity caused by some religious extremists, variously referred to as Boko haram, terrorists, Fulani herdsmen and bandits. The political elites seem to look helpless and Nigerians hopeless as it appears there are no solutions to the menaces.

Ethnicity receives a big boast as Government at the centre, appears unwilling to do what it should do to curtail the situation. Some Nigerians are thus left with no other option than to suspect and accuse the federal government of being sympathetic towards the perpetrators of the violence against the nation. The fact is that the president of Nigeria and the bulk of “troublers” of Nigeria come from the same Fulani ethnic folk. Moreover, appointments into key offices are ethnically biased. The country at present is suffering from all kinds of crises; some of which include, terrorism, banditry, kidnapping, cattle rustling and rape. According to Wegh, Nigerians see the *Boko Haram* campaign as completely motivated by political interests. That is to say there are those who believe that *Boko Haram* is the product of some aggrieved politicians who are determined to make life difficult for those in government by creating a state of insecurity.²⁰ When religious conflicts escalate to serious violent state, resources that are meant for the provision of critical infrastructure that can propel development and social change are diverted to contend with the insecurity that the conflict has created. One may easily submit that security votes to the executives could be one of the reasons for government lackadaisical attitude towards security challenges and failure to take drastic measures to end insecurity in Nigeria.

At the national level, there appears to be heightened- ethnic cleavages more than any time in the history of Nigeria. The result is the formation of ethnic and regional security outfits to defend their territories. Such as Amotekun, Ebube Agwu, Volunteer Guard, Odua People’s Congress (OPC), Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), Eastern Security Network (ESN), Nigerian Forest Guards, etc. Nigerians have lost confidence in the ability of the Federal government in defending them. One will without fear extrapolate that Nigeria is heading to disintegration. Nnoli has identified the negative effects of ethnicity to include:

- i) Division that has plagued all efforts to attain national cohesion and development
- ii) Secession attempts and Civil war
- iii) Violence and inter-ethnic conflicts
- iv) Meritocracy versus mediocrity debate

- v) Disruption of democratic values of justice and fairness
- vi) Waste in the use of economic resources.²¹

We may agree with Nnoli that though ethnicity has positive effects, which are declining with time and change, the negative effects of prejudices, unhealthy promotion of mediocrity to the detriment of meritocracy, conflicts and civil wars have come to stay with us with attendant consequences to include among others expression of secession by different ethnic formations. These have overshadowed the positive effects of ethnicity.

In Nigeria, religion goes hand in hand with ethnicity. At times it is difficult to spot out ethnicity in action and religion. The positive effects of religion on Nigeria are very noticeable. First and foremost, the Christian church pioneered the western education in Nigeria as far back as 1842 at Badagry. Since then the church has taken the lead in the establishment of educational institutions. In this regard Islamic religion is not left out as it has also established many educational institutions in the country. Similarly, both religions are seen active in provision of social amenities, hospitals, modern farms, construction of roads, bridges and other community development projects. The church move in the area of interethnic marriages is the right step in the right direction towards national integration.

However, religion that could have been looked upon as a unifying agent has its own problems. At times religion encourages ethnicity. In Nigeria, Kukah observes that conversion to Christianity was an attractive option for some of the many minority ethnic groups which had experienced tribulations in the hands of what some saw as Hausa/Fulani colonialism and imperialism during and after the jihad.²² Within the same religion, there are denominations and sects that are ethnically based. Perhaps the missionaries fuelled these as means of conserving their flocks within the folds.

Kukah further explains that in the middle belt conversion to Christianity was a way of protesting against Islam. In the southern Nigeria, Christianity brought education as gateway to western civilisation and access to colonial government. So education and religion became mutually reinforcing.²³ Meanwhile, Islam was associated with Hausa/Fulani in the North. At times the less informed southerners refer to all ethnic groups in the north as Hausa and cattle herders as Fulani. While in Christianity, conversion is through preaching and social services, Islam spread through jihad and conquest and was associated with Hausa/Fulani ethnic groups in the North. It appears they had the policy of assimilation at the back of their minds by conquering other ethnic groups and establishing emirates with the Fulani as their emirs.

The negative role of religion is seen in the activities of fundamentalists who perhaps have no in-depth study of their religions and therefore, are indoctrinated to use religion to foment trouble in the country on slightest provocation. Many of such conflicts which many cases emanate from economic and leadership tussle are turned religious to receive a barricade that will exonerate perpetrators from the wrath of the law.

In relation to national integration, there had been controversies over the Nigeria's membership of Organisation of Islamic Countries (OIC), Islamic Bank and implementation of full sharia laws culminating in the establishment of Sharia Appeal Court. Very recently there have been controversy over political parties' presidential candidature which in the local parlance is referred to as "Muslim-Muslim ticket". These issues are capable of tearing Nigeria apart if not well handled. Nevertheless, the government quite aware of the ethnic diversity, has come up with various policies and programmes aimed at achieving national integration. A critical analysis of these reveals that though these have contributed much but the desired integration is not yet achieved.

The Efforts of the Government in Achieving National Integration in Nigeria Constitution

Nigeria has a constitution that describes the rights of every citizen which makes them one in the country irrespective, of religion, ethnic groups or geographical background. A constitution refers to the fundamental laws and principles, which describe and dictate the manner by which a state is governed. It usually contains all institutions and organs of government. It also contains their powers, functions and very basic legal descriptions of what a constitution is.²⁴ Moreover, the Nigerian Constitution in section 17; social objectives, subsections 2(a)

states that: "every citizen shall have equality of rights, obligations and opportunities before the law" while 3(a) states that "All citizens without discrimination on any ground whatsoever, have the opportunity for securing adequate means of livelihood as well as adequate opportunities to secure suitable employment" (Federal Republic of Nigeria, [FRN] (.32-33). However, in practice just as Goubadia observed:

Tensions generated by the application of constitutional provisions which in one breath proclaim one Nigeria nation and citizenship and, in another, give free rein to factors that can reinforce ethnicity and fragmentation in the polity. Alongside creation of one Nigerian citizenship is the emphasis on states and local governments of origin depending on the circumstances end up in ethnicity.²⁵

He further explains that the result of this fragmentation takes the form of preferential policies by state and in discrimination against other Nigerians, so called non-indigenes with respect to state civil service employment and promotion, admission to state educational institutions and public procurement and contract awards contrary to constitutional provisions regarding common and equal Nigerian citizenship rights. At various times, moreover, claims for preferential treatment of state indigenes in federal institutions located in their states of origin have also been asserted in a number of states.

Formation of Political Parties

The government does not allow the political parties to be formed based on ethnic considerations. Each political party is required to show a representation in each of the state of the federation and the federal capital territory. This is aimed at achieving national integration of various ethnic groups who ought to come together and reason as a political party with national interest rather than ethnicity. Section 48 of the 1999 Constitution as amended states that the Senate shall consist of three senators from each state and one from the FCT, Abuja. The Senate is composed on the principle of equality of states which is dominant feature of federating units that guarantees equality of status for the component states.

According to Sections 221-223 of the 1999 constitution, as amended all political parties, the officials and the pattern of party politics must be national in outlook. The essence of these provisions is to avert the emergence of regional or sectional political parties that would definitely represent sectional interests and therefore antithetical to national unity. This noble objective is difficult to achieve, though, a good strategy, it appears at the end of the formations, the parties appear expressing the ethnic interest at a later stage of the three major ethnic groups of Hausa, Yoruba and Ibo with minority ethnic groups aligning to any of the majority.

Attempt was made by the then military government during the General Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida's regime to solve the problem of formation of political parties based on ethnic groups by introducing two party system in the country in 1989. The parties formed and sponsored by the then military regime; Social Democratic Party (SDP) and The National Republican Convention (NRC), were a bold step by the government in the right direction of national integration. One is made to think that the civilian rule would have continued with two party systems not necessary bearing the same names but the parties should not be more than two in the interest of national integration. Nevertheless, it appears within the same party, ethnic and religious politics became noticeable and inevitable, so even one-party system would not necessarily be void of ethnicity and religious considerations and sentiments.

Establishment of Federal Capital Territory

The creation of new Federal Capital was seen as an integrating effort. To this Nkom submits:

National integration was meant to be facilitated by the location and creation of the new Federal Capital at Abuja. A place, to all intents and purposes, fairly equidistant from the farthest parts of Nigeria. It was meant to be a home for all Nigerians -a melting pot of some sort. How far it has been able to achieve this is yet to be determined. It is hoped that the city will offer some hope as the place to begin the process of national integration.²⁶

How this has helped to achieve national integration is still questionable. 'However, the truth remains that as the federal capital many Nigerians are made to live together and learn about each other and live together as one nation. This is likely to enhance national integration. A casual observation would only show the two capitals for the nation. One for the north and one for the south.

National Youths Service Corps (NYSC)

The National Youths Service Corps (NYSC) was created by Decree 24 of 22nd May, 1973 and successfully launched by General Gowon on June 4th 1973. This scheme requires that all Nigerian youths who are thirty years and below who have successfully completed their first degree at any university in Nigeria and abroad to be called upon to serve in the service corps for a duration of one year. This was aimed at bringing Nigerian youths together under a single umbrella, with the objective of instilling in them those virtues of dedication, patriotism and national consciousness without which no country or people can be truly developed. And without which young people cannot have the desire to aspire to be future leaders of this nation. The NYSC scheme has the added advantage of fostering inter-ethnic and interstate understanding which is absolutely essential to nation building.²⁷

However, with the current insecurity status of the country this approach may not succeed Uche Umehuche and Chigozie Okonkwo observe that the status of the National Youth Service Corps as an instrument for national unity has been queried in the event of the gruesome murder of corps members during the post 2011 election crisis and the sectarian violence perpetrated against hapless corps members by the Boko Haram Islamists in some Northern states of Nigeria. They further explain that many Nigerians have called for the outright repealing of the NYSC Act. They cited Afe Babalola and Okochie to support their argument that national unity cannot be brought about by sending students to states where security of lives cannot be guaranteed. It requires more than sending hapless youth to premature death. And that although, the NYSC was instituted as an instrument for national unity; events of the past few years have resulted to frantic calls for the scrapping of the programme because it has become an object of mockery and rejection. It is not a surprise that because of the harrowing experiences of the corps members they do not preach the "gospel of national unity". This is a huge drag to the efforts at national unity; given that these groups of Nigerians are the future of the nation.²⁸

The Establishment of Unity Schools

Another way of enhancing national integration is the establishment of federal schools otherwise referred to as unity schools in all the states of the federation. At least two federal secondary schools are established in each state and admission into these schools is expected to cut across all states and ethnic groups in Nigeria. Equally, the appointment of staff to these schools and colleges is supposed to follow the federal character. This is intended to achieve togetherness, cultural and religious integration. This approach too has its own problems as the children from the educationally disadvantaged states and poor family background are often discriminated upon instead of proper integration.

Federal Character Commission

Another effort to promote national integration is the establishment of federal character Commission with the quota system as a principle to ensure that in every federal government establishment each state of the federation is represented in the sharing of national resources so that ethnic/religious marginalisation is avoided. Hitherto, it was alleged that the Yoruba dominated the federal civil service. "Igbo dominated the police, while the Hausa/Fulani dominated the army. The nearness of southerners to Lagos, the federal capital as well as perhaps the unwillingness of literates from the north at the time to accept federal appointments, due to better opportunities in their region, all aided disproportionate recruitment".²⁹ Recruitment in the federal civil service, military, admission into federal universities is now based on quota system. Federal character principle is, in part, designed to deal with the problem of imbalance, marginalisation and discrimination. The question then arises as to whether

the principle can be rightly used to address the problem of discrimination in the composition and conduct of public institutions and affairs and ensure effective integration of various sections of the Nigerian society.³⁰

This has achieved much but it appears as Okwudiba Nnoli has pointed out, there are pitfalls in the implementation of federal character. Ethnicity has become wide spread. He observes that in the past it was limited to relations among language groups, today it has led to ethnic like antagonisms within language groups. He concludes that with federal character, “the country is not only faced with the prospect of polarisation at the national level but also at the regional and local levels”.³¹

Sports

The cultural diversity of Nigerians appears vanished when it comes to games and sports. The national teams that represent Nigeria have membership drawn from different religious and ethnic groups in the country and Nigerians at home and diaspora cheer up the teams for victory as Nigerians. One is tempted to think that the national games and sports festivals are the very best avenues for national integration, and of course the government sponsors sports in the country for the purpose of national integration. This approach also has the limitation of fully reflecting the federal character as selection of team members is sometimes biased and not on talent and skills for each game or sport and not all states have hosting capacity for national sports festivals.

National Festivals

The organisation of national festivals like Democracy day, Independence Day and national sports festivals are equally good avenues for enhancing national integration. The Nigerian people are made to come together to celebrate these on yearly bases both at grass root and national levels and this stirs up the spirit of nationalism.

National symbols

An entity is identified by symbolic expressions. Nigeria has national symbols that help remind us that we are of one identity and of course national integration. 'Every Nigerian identifies with the nation through the national symbols. These consist of the National Flag, Coat of Arms, National Pledge, National Anthem, Constitution and the Nigerian Currency. The national identity is more or less a psychological or spiritual quality which unites the people of a nation'.³² Nigerians should therefore show greater and proper respect for the national symbols not just in times of celebrations but at all times and everywhere.

States and Local Government Creation

The demand and desperation for the creation of states and local government councils in Nigeria over the years has been provoked by ethnic marginalisation. In Benue state for instance, the Tiv ethnic group is the most dominant group in the state. It has been producing the civilian executive governors since the creation of the state. In the second republic the chief executive was Aper Aku, in Third Republic it was Moses Orshio Adasu, in the Fourth Republic it was George Akume, after which was Gabriel Suswan and today is Samuel Ortom.

The Idoma who are a minority ethnic group have been crying foul play over the political marginalisation in the state. They feel the way out is the creation of ‘Apa State’ a project they have been upon for a long period now. This is just one case out of several calls by minority ethnic groups for state creation in the country. While one would think that the Idoma do not condone discrimination and marginalisation, since the return to civilian rule, Igede have not produced a senator from zone C to which the Idoma are the majority. This is in line with what Okwudiba Nnoli had earlier noticed that state creation does not permanently solve the problem of the people who still feel marginalised, as each exercise has given rise to demand for more states.³³ National Assembly had over 30 demands from different ethnic groups in the country demanding for states of their own when proposals were made for the creation of more states in the country. Ahmed and Dantata had observed with surprise that state creation has increased the nation’s disunity and sense of alienation. Non-indigenes are treated little better than aliens in states other than their own. Even if they so wish, non-indigenes cannot integrate where they work, pay

their taxes and may even have been born. Restrictions are placed on the rights to own property: they tend to be confined as in colonial times in specific residential quarters (Sabon -Gari), that constitute easy target in case of social, religious, communal unrest. In the field of education, non-indigenes are required to pay higher school fees in some states.³⁴

A close look at the efforts by the government shows that much efforts have been made to overcome religion and ethnicity but with very little success. Therefore the main problems tearing Nigeria apart, are still religion and ethnicity. The paper now address the issue of religion and the challenges to national integration in Nigeria.

Religion, Ethnicity and the Challenges to National Integration in Nigeria

The Loss Legacy:

1. In 1950 in Lagos, Olorunimbe was the 1st Mayor of Lagos with Mazi Mbonu Ojike as his deputy.
2. In 1952, Chief Ekwuyasi from Ogwashi Ukwu represented Benin west in the Western House of Assembly.
3. In 1950, Mallam Umaru Altine (a Fulani man) was elected mayor twice in Enugu.
4. In 1957 Felix Okonwo (an Ibo man) was a special member of the Northern House of Chiefs in Kano.
5. In 1959, Mallam Umaru Yushau (the Sarkin Hausawa) in Onitsha was elected a member of the Eastern House of Chiefs.
6. 1961, the Aba people voted Margaret Ekpo to represent them and Ababiliki voted Chief Eyo Bassey (father of AK APC Pub Sec) both non-Igbos into parliament.
7. Alh. Ibrahim Abubakar Imam (from Maiduguri) once represented the Tiv in the House of Representatives.
8. Obafemi Awolowo once led the Campaign for Ernest Ikoli (an Ijaw man) who defeated Chief Akinsanya in an Election in Lagos.
9. Nnamdi Azikiwe led the NCNC to a clean sweep of Legislative Seats in Lagos (web).

So where have we got it wrong today that we are so divided along religion and ethnic linings? Many scholars try to blame ethnicity on colonialism. Alemika argues that the colonial government promoted divisions and disunity among the indigenous peoples in order to facilitate colonial exploitation and domination without large-scale resistance. He further argued that colonial government's actions created much of the grounds for accusations of marginalisation and dominion after independence as well as the disagreement between northern and southern representatives in the colonial legislature in 1953. Nigerians have built on this colonial formation and have continued to operate along the lines of divisions created by the colonialists.³⁵

While it is easy and very tempting to blame the colonialists for all of Nigeria's woes, history and recent events in the country have revealed that the covert selfishness, hunger for power and primitive accumulation of wealth exhibited by the political elites are main causes of ethnicity. That is to say ethnicity is a formation by politicians to create sentiments in the minds of the ignorant and helpless citizens to achieve selfish interest. It is a means by which many political leaders exploit for personal advantages. Religion too has been used as a tool for manipulation of the masses by the political class thereby tearing the masses apart. If one looks at Nigeria, everything bears the frightful eyes of a dichotomy: the north-south dichotomy, South-East dichotomy, South-West dichotomy, Christian-Muslim dichotomy, military – civilian dichotomy, bourgeoisie – proletariat dichotomy, literate-illiterate dichotomy, etc.

Nigerians are so divided along religious and ethnic lines that an average Tiv, Igbo, Hausa or Yoruba person first thinks of himself as Hausa or Igbo before thinking that he is Muslim or Christian. This division is seen in almost everything we do. It is seen in:

- (1) Appointments into key offices such as heads of MDAs, the legislature, executive, judiciary, armed forces and para-military agencies, etc.
- (2) Employment into key government offices of NNPC, down to the universities. Many Nigeria Federal Universities have gone tribal talk less of state universities.

- (3) Recruitment into the military/para-military agencies.
- (4) Admission into institutions of higher learning, military institutions, unity schools and even course allocation (e. g. medicine, pharmacy, engineering, nursing, etc) are all based on religion and ethnicity. This accounts for the declining standards and examination misconduct has been institutionalised in the school system. Admissions are given on religious/ethnic grounds and not on merit. Academic staff are also recruited most times on religious/ethnic grounds. Vice-chancellor's lists are often full of candidates based on religious/ethnic sentiments because they want to please the powers that be or their principals.
- (5) Marriages are also done according to religious and ethnic lines.
- (6) Formation of political parties in Nigeria for long has been on religious/ethnic lines. The Northern People's Congress (NPC) and the National Party of Nigeria (NPN) were parties for the Muslims and later APP because of Governor Ahmed Sani Yerima who was a member and supporter of the Sharia Law. Other political parties formed on religious and ethnic linings include Action Group (AG), Tiv Progressive Union, Middle Belt Peoples Party (MBPP), Middle Zone League (MZL) and Birom Progressive Union (BPU). The present case of Muslim/Muslim or Christian-Christian ticket is ongoing in Nigeria as the 2023 election approaches.
- (7) Hangmen Death Warrant is signed or not signed by Governors based on religious or ethnic sentiments. Thus, while the death warrants of some convicted to die by hanging is quickly signed, others are not signed for many years depending on their religious and or ethnic lining.

Consequently, the first hurdle in the path of national integration in Nigeria has been a regenerative breed of selfish politicians and greedy political gladiators who seize power through the barrel of the gun or through stolen electoral mandates. As they compete for power, prestige and associated benefits, the political elites in a bid to secure the support of members of their own ethnic/religious groups accentuate ethnic/religious differences and demonise members of other ethnic/religious groups. For instance, during the first republic, in Benue State. J.S. Tarka came home and informed Jato Aka that he had the ambition of liberating the Tiv from the tyrannical rule of the Hausa. He received his spiritual blessings and left. But when he failed, he mobilised his ethnic group and led a revolt against the ruling Political party Northern Peoples' Congress (NPC) whose members were nicknamed among the Tiv as Hausa. However, during the second republic the same J.S, Tarka pitched camp with the Hausa in a bid to become the president of the country. A dream he never achieved.

Secondly, corruption has so permeated the entire fabric of state that the issues that cause disaffection among ethnic nationalities in the country such as poverty, hunger, illiteracy and its attendant limited opportunities, unemployment, marginalisation, infrastructural decay, homelessness and lack of access to quality health care are products of corruption. Rather than look to the West to find solutions for corruption, Nigeria should begin to look to the East (Asia) where capital or severe punishment is meted out on corrupt state officials. Skewed federal system as it is being practiced in Nigeria today is another challenge for national integration.

The fear of losing control by the ruling class is another issue standing in the path of national integration in Nigeria. For many years now, the people of Nigeria have continuously canvassed for an opportunity to hold a national conversation to address the present political configuration called Nigeria all to no avail. Nnoli Iheanacho and Nwagwu have contended that the ruling class in Nigeria inherited a state structure and has left it without any form of modification or moderation up until now. According to them, instead, the ruling class is preoccupied with the use of state paraphernalia for accumulating surplus without producing this surplus. The resultant contradiction is an institutionalised myopic and visionless ethnic-centred leadership with separatist and particularistic political outlook.³⁶

Onifade and Imhonopi argue that federalism as it is presently practiced in Nigeria suffers because of lack of fiscal federalism, over-centralisation of power at the centre, laidback or non-viable states, absence of state police, among others. More importantly, federalism in Nigeria has failed to guarantee national integration on one hand and yet fails to guarantee local rule on the other hand. According to them, although Nigeria does not have a

better option for democracy, it cannot continue to administer the polity based on the existing federal arrangement. This calls for restructuring.³⁷

Again, lack of political will to do the right thing by the political leadership has remained one reason the country has continued to flounder in the sea of confusion and tottering the precipice of religious and ethnic division. Another hurdle to realising national integration in Nigeria is the existence of weak institutions of the state. It seems these institutions are kept weak to further the political and economic fortunes of the ruling class. In Nigeria, it is criminal to be honest and honest to be criminal. Such weak, embryonic, sterile, insensitive and amoral characteristics of state institutions have further tilted Nigeria to the precipice.³⁸

Not only that, lack of fairness, justice and equity in the country with regard to resource allocation and distribution, power sharing, enjoyment of fundamental human rights and punishment of criminals who hide under political umbrellas or bunkers created by the ruling class takes the country backwards with regard to national cohesion.³⁹ When leaders engage in all these they use ethnicity and religion to cover up so as to enjoy the applause of their supportive groups to the detriment of national integration.

Insecurity: Nigeria has serious security challenges ranging from poverty, unemployment, kidnapping for ransom and or rituals, terrorism, armed banditry, Fulani herdsman attacks on farmers, human/drugs trafficking, as well as social vices such as prostitution, commercial sex, cultism, etc. Infact, one cannot quantify the numbers of people kidnapped in Nigeria apart from the Chibok school girls and Leah Sharibu who has remained in captivity for not renouncing her faith.

Indeed, crises regarded as religious are mostly triggered by ethnic socio-economic and political interest. The 1st military coup d'état by major Nzeagu where Sir Ahmadu Bello the Saraduna of Sokoto was killed had religious/ethnic colouration. Similarly, the killing of major General Aguiyi Ironsi the then military Head of State in a bloody coup on 29th January, 1966 was said to be reprisal attacks by the Northern military for killing Sir Ahmadu Bello, a Muslim leader from the North by a Christian Army, Major Kaduna Nzeagu from the South. Religion was one of the factors that led to the Biafra war (1967-1970) that claimed over 600,000 lives.⁴⁰

Other issues that have given birth to the tension between Christians and Muslims include:

- (a) The formation of Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN)
- (b) The inclusion of Nigeria in the Organisation of Islamic Conference. Christians see this as a ploy to Islamise Nigeria.
- (c) The introduction of the Sharia Law. Indeed, the implementation of Sharia Law in some states brought about religious unrest, violence and annihilation of some Christians.

Communal and religious conflicts in Nigeria: The origin of religious conflicts in Nigeria could be traced to the colonial period when the British amalgamated the northern and southern protectorates in 1914 each with different religious persuasion. These conflicts are mostly between Muslims and Christians. Some of these crises include: the Maitasine riot (1980-1985), Kafanchan College of Education riot (1987), the reaction to Reinhard Bonke's Crusade in Bauchi (1990), Kano (1991), Zangon-Kataf (1992), Sharia Crises in Kaduna 2000, Bauchi 2001, Jos 2001, Yelwan-Shendam ethno-religious crises 2004, Kano reaction to Yelwan-Shendam religious crises, 2004. In December 1994, an Igbo man was beheaded by the Muslim fundamentalist group, the Shiites for using the Quran in the toilet. At present, the Boko Haram insurgency has a very serious security implication on the unity of the nation.

Towards National Integration in Nigeria

This paper believes that national integration in Nigeria has bright prospects and therefore makes the following suggestions:

- i. **Restructuring:** The Federal System of Government should have less powers. More revenue should be allocated to the states. Funds should be shared to the local Governments directly and the office of the chairman of a local Government should be rotational so that all ethnic groups and districts would benefit

from the office. Again, we need only one Legislative House (House of Representatives) to cut down expenditure.

- ii. The need to de-emphasise religion and ethnicity on official documents as for example when completing official forms for either employment, admission etc. For instance, the Nigerian passport has no such on it. Religion must embrace peace, morality, unity, love, humility and forgiveness religiously.

We need to focus more attention on the role of political parties in Nigeria. It is through political parties that Nigerian leaders emerge. Political parties must ensure inclusivity and avoid religious and ethnic sentiments. Political parties should ensure internal democracy and avoid dirty politics and nasty political language, rigging, thuggery and violence.

There is a need for the Peace Accord Committee headed by Gen. Abdulsalami to continue to function in all elections. The peace committee should ensure that all stakeholders and political parties sign a peace accord before every election and abide by it. Failure to which sanctions should be applied. There should be sincerity in inter-religious dialogue. The committee on inter-religious dialogue must work harder to ensure peaceful coexistence between the two religions.

Enhancing the *es spirit de corps* for national unity: *Es spirit de corps* is a term referring to the unity and solidarity shared by the military and para-military. This friendship cuts across all military and para-military formations, religious and ethnic groups. If all Nigerians embrace this culture, irrespective of their religion and ethnic group, this will foster national integration in the country. Harvesting sports solidarity for national integration in Nigeria. During sports competitions especially football, all Nigerians unite despite their religious and ethnic affiliations to support Nigerian players. This type of comradeship should be embraced in all situations to enhance national integration in Nigeria.

Leaders at all levels should be people who are versatile, with a sound educational background in public administration. The leaders should be competent and knowledgeable who have a known academic history in an area of specialisation. A system where a school certificate holder heads the public office making policies for the educated would never lead to peace and national integration.

Need for equity/fair distribution of federal and state appointments: As the Nigerian Constitution has stated, the federal character principle should be applied in all situations. In political appointments, recruitment in the military/para-military, employment in all government offices, admission into unity schools, etc.

Religious leaders should define their doctrines in the light of the present realities. Change is constant and therefore the prophets and leaders should relate with God in such ways that will receive new messages that would address man's problems in the contemporary Nigeria. Government should make strong policy against religious fundamentalism in the country and alien preachers should abide by them when they come to preach in the country. Again, government at various levels should give equal considerations to all religions. They should not over protect one religion against another. They should however, check against excesses by the adherents of the aggressive alien religions.

Another effort put in place for national integration is inter-ethnic marriages. According to Kyernum Nyamibo, inter-ethnic marriage encourages national integration. When this occurs, there is cultural integration whether consciously or unconsciously. It grinds down the fears that these ethnic groups might have been nursing before. All the social institutions should work towards encouraging inter-ethnic marriages in Nigeria as weapon against disunity in the country. Very importantly, the church encourages marriage across ethnic groups wiping away the ethnic fears and dichotomies. The church is the leading agency in propagating inter-ethnic marriage. In this regard it appears the Pentecostals are leading groups in propagating inter-ethnic marriages.⁴¹

Moreover, the Bible teaches that there should not be any discrimination in terms of sex, ethnic group or race, hence all are members of the body of Christ: "There is neither Jew nor Greek, there is neither bond nor free, there is neither male or female: for ye are all one in Christ Jesus"(Galatians 3.28). In the light of this conviction, church membership cuts across different ethnic groups in the country where members are regarded and recognised as brothers and sisters. Priests are transferred to serve in different states and Bishoprics regardless

of their ethnic background. This is a giant step in national integration.⁴² Though this too has some problems as some priests are asked to go back to their ethnic groups and preach there.

Conclusion

Religion and ethnicity are key issues in national integration in Nigeria. They contribute in one way or the other, for nation building. However, the political elites and fundamentalists use them to create sentiments, prejudices that lead to ethnic and religious conflicts with attendant negative consequences that constitute a threat to national integration. The federal government and the religious bodies have equally made efforts in achieving national integration. These efforts noble as they are conceived turnout to further increase ethnicity and religious conflicts. Corruption, leadership failure and failed political interest are the reasons behind ethnicity and religious disintegration in Nigeria. While hoping that government would give equal protection for religions in their domain, the state structure of the federal government should be scrapped and the local government strengthened to minimise religion/ethnicity to boast development in Nigeria. Though tribe and tongue may differ, in brotherhood we stand, so let us stand together or we shall all lost whether Christian, Muslim, Tiv, Itsekiri, Ijaw, Urhobo, Yoruba, Igbo, Hausa or Fulani. Let all stand as one and save our nation together because we have only one Nigeria that has the potential to lead Africa.

Endnotes

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